

Professional Stress amongst Teaching Professionals

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ABSTRACT

Occupational stress can be considered as the damaging physical and emotional response occurring with unmatched potentials, resources and requirements of the professional. Occupational stress may lead to poor health and sometimes even to damages

The topic "Occupational Stress amongst teaching professionals" was chosen with the view of considering the effect of occupational stress amongst teaching professionals of Ranchi District. The other purpose was to find out how they deal with stress particularly in higher educational organisations. 50 faculty members were selected from higher educational institutions. Data was collected by using questionnaire method. The sample was selected through Random Judgemental sampling method. The sample of research study included all teaching positions who were related to teaching with different designation such as lab instructor, lecturer, assistant professors, associate professors, and professors.

The responses of respondents were calculated on the basis of various stressors such as: total class load, administrative work load, work conditions, class control, relationship with other colleagues, Salary and other benefits, social recognition, lack of infrastructure, time deadlines.

This paper aims at studying the various reasons leading to organisational stress amongst the teaching professionals of various universities and colleges of Ranchi district. The parameters for measuring the effects of stress were kept subjective rather than objective.

KEYWORDS: Occupational stress, Teaching professionals, Higher educational institutions, Stressors

INTRODUCTION

Earlier teaching was considered as one of the easiest and least stressed jobs, but with passing time teaching is no longer considered as only hard work but also highly stressful profession. This has gradually turned into a highly stressful and difficult profession. Professors face new challenges as the students' population is becoming more diverse. Faculty members are required to develop newer skills and knowledge to cope up with the changing requirements. This often leads to excess of pressure and challenges for the faculty, this consequently leads to occupational stress.

Occupational stress amongst teaching professionals may be defined as "the experience by a teacher of unpleasant, negative emotions, such as anxiety, tension, frustration or depression, resulting from some aspects. Occupational stress amongst the teaching professionals, confine the quality of teaching staffs and the same creates misery amongst them. Heavy workload, unsecured state of job, low pay emoluments, lack of career development, lack of communication, harassments in the University or college by peer teachers/workers/students/others, financial problems. Can be considered as the reasons of stress amongst the teaching faculties. Continuous stress leads to lack of peacefulness amongst the teachers. It also has negative impact on their work performance Teachers' stress may be defined as the experience by a teacher of unpleasant, negative emotions, such as anger, anxiety, tension,

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frustration or depression, resulting from some aspect of their work as a teacher (Kyriacou 2001).

Objectives

1. To find out the various reasons leading to occupational stress amongst teaching professionals of Universities and Colleges.
2. To find out the least significant occupational stressor.
3. To find out the most significant occupational stressor.

Literature Review

(Gabha, 2013) Professional stress has become one of the real challenges that teachers working in various Universities and Colleges have to face. This stress affects the work environment negatively, so it is important that the institutions regularly monitor for stress related problems and help its employees in overcoming the stress faced by them.

(Curelaru, Muntele Hendreş, & Farcaş, 2013) Factors causing stress amongst teachers should be explored regularly and effective coping strategies should be developed for dealing with the existing stress.

(Chowdhury, 2012) Faculty members at the University of Pakistan is witnessing a moderate level of occupational stress. However a large number of respondents (67%)state

that occupational stress is not a very big problem. Only a very small number of respondents stated occupational stress as a big problem.

(Chaudhry Abdul Gayoom, 2012) In order to test the relationship between job satisfaction and overall professional stress amongst the faculty members of Universities and Colleges Pearson's Correlation method was applied. In accordance with the table's statistics, there are no statistically significant differences between job satisfaction and professional stress and found the overall relationship.

(Merike Darmody and Emer Smyth, 2011) In their study on occupational satisfaction and occupational stress amongst primary school teachers and school Principals in Ireland, found that 45% of teachers and 70% of Principals have experienced job-related stress

(Jayashree Nayak, 2008) Stated that 28.5% of (34% of male and 23% of female teachers) college teachers regularly face occupational stress due to the complicated nature of job. The findings were based on her study of factors affecting occupational stress and coping strategies amongst the degree college faculties of Dharwad city

(Brewer and Landers, 2003) Found in their study the relationship between work and job stress by studying the sample of teachers belonging from teaching institutions. They found out that there is an inverse relationship between organisational structure and work stress. They also concluded job stress is the main factor which influences the level of employees' job satisfaction.

(Kyriacou et al., 2003) found that occupational stress affects negatively in teachers' retention. Factors such as emoluments, workload, disturbing students and lack of career advancement may be considered as the reasons behind occupational stress amongst teachers.

(Pestonjee and Azeem, 2001) conducted a study on "Research on the Pressure of Organizational Role of University Teachers" "Job Burnout" and found that teachers are facing continuous occupational stress, as a result of which they face both mental as well as physical disorder.

(Schaufeli and Enzmann, 1998) analysed 73 different studies relating to the United States with an objective to find out which occupation-related field is more vulnerable to stress. They found that emotional fatigue level is high amongst the teachers.

(Vance, Miller, Humphreys & Reynolds 1989) in their study, pointed out that on an average 30,000 teachers involved in teaching wants to leave their profession every year to stay away from the stressful job condition. Stress in teaching profession is acknowledged extensively and it was found that their mental health is significantly poorer than that of many other high stressed professions

(King and Peart, 1992) found that about 66% of teachers had strongly considered parting from the teaching occupation as a result of severe job-related stress.

(Wilson, 1979) Stated in his work "Teaching Teachers to De-stress" that 90% of teachers in California experienced at least some kind of occupational stress and 95% of teachers are willing to participate in some kind of stress coping training workshop, so that they can deal with stress more effectively.

Research Methodology

A sample size of 50 respondents including teaching professionals was selected for the study. All the respondents belonged from various Universities and Colleges of Ranchi, such as Ranchi University, XISS, BIT Mesra, Sarala Birla University, Usha Martin University etc. Judgemental Sampling method was used to select the required sample. Questionnaire method was used to collect the required data. The sample of research study included all teaching positions who were related to teaching with different designation such as lab instructor, lecturer, assistant professors, associate professors, and professors.

Hypothesis

4. Null Hypothesis H₀: There are various factors that leads to occupational stress amongst faculty members of University and Colleges.
5. Alternate Hypothesis H₁: There are no factors leading to occupational stress amongst faculty members of University and Colleges.

Major Occupational Stressors

Following parameters were considered as the major occupational stressors for the study:

1. Total class load
2. Ambiguous job description
3. Lack of support
4. Class control
5. relationship with colleagues
6. Salary and other benefits
7. Social recognition
8. Frequent reshuffling of syllabus and subjects
9. Time deadlines
10. 24 Hours of involvement

Data Analysis

In the given table the respondents are shown as per their age, gender, educational qualification and total work experience. It was observed that most of the respondents belonged to the age group 31years to 40 years (43%), following which was the age group below 30 years (23%). Whereas the other age groups consisted of (16%) each. When looking at Educational qualifications, it was observed that majority of respondents were having master's degree (70%) followed by MS/M.Phil. (16 %) followed by Ph.D holders (14%). When talking about work experience, it was observed that 32% respondents had less than five years experiences, 40% percent respondent had between 5 to 10 years experiences, 14% percent respondents had between 11 to 20 years' experience, 14% percent respondents had more than twenty years' experience in the teaching.

Table: 01 (demographic factors of respondents)

Sl. No.	Category	Criteria	Number of Respondents
1.	Age	below30	12
		31-40	23
		41-50	8
		51and above	8
2.	Gender	Male	32
		Female	18
3.	Educational Qualification	Masters	35
		MS/M.Phil.	8
		Ph.D.	7
4.	Work Experience	Below 5 Years	16
		5years-10 years	20
		11years-20 years	7
		Above21 years	7

Factors that can lead to occupational stress:

Table: 02 (Effect of Various Occupational Stressors)

S. No	Occupational Stressor	Level of Stress			
		Very High	Moderate	Low	Never
1.	Total class load	5	28	9	8
2.	Ambiguous job description	9	20	18	3
3.	Lack of Support	16	22	8	4
4.	Class control	0	12	19	19
5.	relationship with colleagues	6	27	13	5
6.	Salary and other benefits	33	14	3	0
7.	Social recognition	10	19	13	7
8.	Frequent reshuffling of syllabus and subjects	17	19	10	4
9.	Time deadlines	20	12	10	8
10.	24 Hours of involvement	21	22	5	2

Fig: (Occupational stressors amongst faculties)

Discussion and Conclusion

On viewing the above data, it can be stated that amongst the various occupational stressors salary and other benefits is one of the most stressing factors found amongst the teaching faculties. On the other hand, relationship with other staffs and total class load did not lead to much of stress amongst the faculties.

This study can be fruitful to understand how we can increase the employees' level of motivation followed by their work performance.

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